

Historical development of legal regulation in the business sector in the Middle East, in the period: 1950-1999

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the article is to study the historical development of legal regulation of business in the Middle East over a certain period of time. For this purpose, the object of study is the historical period from the beginning of 1950 to 1999. Thus, the scientific task is to consider how the business sector in the Middle East developed and evolved throughout the twentieth century. Thus, the research methodology involves the use of the historical method and the method of hermeneutics. These methods contributed to the key findings of the study. As a result, the historical development of the legal regulation of the business sector in the Middle East was carried out. The author's view of the key historical stages of business regulation in a particular country is characterized and presented. It was pointed out which specific laws were created, which policies were introduced and which were the main regulated companies of that period. However, the study is limited by considering only one country in the Middle East - Jordan. Prospects for future research suggest taking into account the 21st century according to its characteristics.

Keywords: History of law, Legal regulation, Historical factors, Middle East, Legal aspects.

Desarrollo histórico de la regulación jurídica en el sector empresarial de Oriente Medio, en el período: 1950-1999

RESUMEN

El objetivo principal del artículo es estudiar el desarrollo histórico de la regulación legal de los negocios en el Medio Oriente durante un cierto período de tiempo. Para ello, el objeto de estudio es el período histórico comprendido entre principios de 1950 y 1999. Por tanto, la tarea científica es considerar cómo se desarrolló y desarrolló el sector empresarial en Oriente Medio a lo largo del siglo XX. Así, la metodología de la investigación implica el uso del método histórico y el método de la hermenéutica. Estos métodos contribuyeron a los hallazgos clave del estudio. Como resultado, se llevó a cabo el desarrollo histórico de la regulación legal del sector empresarial en Medio Oriente. Se caracteriza y presenta la visión del autor de las etapas históricas clave de la regulación empresarial en un país en particular. Se señaló qué leyes específicas se crearon, qué políticas se introdujeron y cuáles fueron las principales empresas reguladas de ese período. Sin embargo, el estudio se ve limitado al considerar sólo un país de Oriente Medio: Jordania. Las perspectivas de futuras investigaciones sugieren tener en cuenta el siglo XXI según sus características.

Palabras clave: Historia del derecho, Regulación legal, Factores históricos, Medio Oriente, Aspectos legales.

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Introduction

The question of studying the historical origins of the legal regulation of companies in the Middle East, particularly in the period from the 1950s to the 1990s of the twentieth century, is relevant from the point of view of scientific and practical interest. This is due to the fact that this period was characterized by the manifestation of a series of historical, political, economic and social changes in the Middle East. These historical changes are associated with the discovery of oil sources, the intensification of decolonization processes after World War II and the development of the Cold War, with all its geopolitical problems and constraints. All these and other historical events led to a significant development of the legal and business environment (Radpey and Rose, 2017).

Moreover, it was during this period that the first manifestations of globalization processes intensified in the Middle East, where the region played a key role, since a large amount of energy resources - oil - was located in this territory. In order to understand the historical trajectory of the integration of a given region into the global economy, it is also important to examine the then legal framework for these processes, as well as the peculiarities of the influence of international legal norms on the regional business environment (Godley and Shechter, 2008).

Thus, from the mid-1950s, innovative laws and other legal acts began to emerge in the legal systems of the largest countries in the Middle East, the formation of which took place in the synthesis of traditional Islamic law and Western legal paradigms. Understanding the essence of this synthesis is key to analyzing the modern legal regulation of the business sector in the Middle East. The formation of this new legal framework was significantly influenced by the political and military conflicts that began at that time, as well as by the new economic unions in the region and the world.

Over time, the new legal regulation of the business sector also became a factor influencing these economic, political and social changes, as it updated the role of civilized forms of conflict resolution and the preference for the development of economic cooperation. The new legal regulation of the business sector has greatly influenced the ways of utilizing new energy resources and ensuring uninterrupted sustainable economic development in the region (Sidani and Thornberry, 2010).

Understanding the evolution and development of legal regulation of the business sector in the Middle East from the 1950s to the 1990s is useful knowledge not only for historians and scholars, but also for politicians, economists and lawyers, as it provides information on the origins of modern problems and trends in the economic development of the business sector, as well as on the possible legal prospects for the development of this field in the future. For these reasons, the main objective of the article was to analyze the historical basis of the legal regulation of the business sector in the Middle East during the period 1950-1990.

1. Survey of documentary sources in digital format

Examining the historical evolution of legal regulation in the Middle Eastern business sector, specifically during the period 1950-1999, requires a review of the existing literature that addresses the intersections between legal frameworks, business practices and the socio-political dynamics of this historically troubled region. This literature review draws on a wide range of scholarly contributions, ranging from the study of trust and commitment in business relationships, to the role of political parties in democratization processes, the tensions between Islamic ideals and business practices, the historical evolution of human rights concepts, and the institutional factors contributing to economic underdevelopment in the Middle East in general.

Abosag and Lee (2013) delve into the cultural underpinnings of business relationships in the Middle East through their exploration of Et-Moone relationships, offering valuable insights into the formation of trust and commitment. While this research illuminates aspects of business culture, their focus on interpersonal relationships provides a complementary perspective to our analysis of formal legal regulations and their historical development. Similarly, AbuKhalil's (1997) analysis of political parties and democratization in the Arab world sheds light on the broader political contexts in which legal regulations evolve. Although democratization processes indirectly influence business environments, the emphasis of our study on legal regulations as a primary factor in the development of the business sector requires a more direct examination of legal texts and policies.

Ahmad (2007) addresses the juxtaposition of Islamic ideals with business practices, highlighting ethical considerations within the Middle Eastern business sector. While this contribution enriches the understanding of cultural and religious influences on business ethics, our research focuses more on the specific legal frameworks regulating business operations. For their part, Aznagulova et al., (2021) trace the idea of human rights from antiquity to the digital age, offering a broad historical sweep that situates the Middle East within a global history of human rights.

While these works provide valuable context, our study requires a closer examination of the specific legal regulations affecting the business sector. Bates (1986) explores the first century of Islamic coinage to establish connections between history, geography, and numismatics. While Bates' numismatic approach offers insight into the economic history of the region, our research focuses more on legal texts and their direct impact on business practices. In this context, Djono et al., (2022) and Horiacheva et al., (2023) offer historical perspectives on leadership transformation and military political leadership, respectively. These studies, while offering important historical perspectives, diverge from our approach to legal regulation in the business sector.

Kuran (2004) critically analyzes the historical mechanisms of institutional stagnation in the Middle East, attributing economic underdevelopment to enduring but pre-modern institutional frameworks. Kuran's work coincides closely with our interest in historical legal frameworks, but emphasizes economic outcomes over the specifics of legal changes. In this vein,

Marchuk et al., (2020) discuss the role of the philosophy of history in understanding the challenges of modern civilization in a post-pandemic society. Summarizing, in the above analysis, we have identified key gaps in the above literature sources (Table 1).

Table 1. The main thematic or conceptual gaps on the topic

Thematic failures or gaps	Characteristics
Regional specificity and depth of legal analysis	One of the notable gaps in the existing literature is the lack of in-depth, region-specific analyses that explore the historical development of the legal frameworks governing business practices in the Middle East, with particular attention to individual countries. While there is extensive research on the cultural, economic, and political aspects of the Middle East business environment, there is a dearth of studies that delve into the detailed evolution of legal regulations, their historical contexts, and the specific impacts on the business sector within individual countries such as Jordan. Therefore, our research fills this gap by providing a historical examination focused on the development of legal regulation, highlighting the enactment of specific laws and policies, in the period studied.
Integration of the Historical Method and Hermeneutics in Business Law Research	Another gap in the selected literature is the underuse of historical methods and hermeneutic analysis in the study of the legal regulation of business. Most studies tend to focus on contemporary legal frameworks or adopt a predominantly socio-economic perspective without engaging deeply with the historical evolution of legal texts and their interpretative analysis. By employing both the historical method and hermeneutics, our study offers a comprehensive understanding of the progression and contextual meanings of legal regulations affecting the business sector in the Middle East, bridging the methodological gap in existing research.
Specificity of legal developments and their impact on business practices	The scientific literature on the subject often overlooks the detailed examination of how specific legal developments directly influenced business practices and corporate governance in the Middle East. While acknowledging the general influence of legal and regulatory environments on economic activities, there is a gap in detailed studies that trace the direct links between certain legal norms, their historical evolution and their impact on the operational and strategic dimensions of enterprises. In contrast, our research addresses this gap by identifying and characterizing key legal regulations and policies introduced during the second half of the 20th century and analyzing their specific effects on the business sector in Jordan.

Source: (Prepared by the author).

Overall, the literature reviewed provides valuable insights into the cultural, political and ethical dimensions of business activity in the Middle East. However, these studies do not fully address the specific historical development of legal regulation in the region's business sector between 1950 and 1999. Our research fills this gap by providing a detailed examination of the legal frameworks that directly influenced business practices and governance in the Middle East, with a particular focus on Jordan. Through this specific analysis, we aim to contribute to the development of a nuanced understanding of the legal landscape that shaped the business environment during a critical period of economic and social transformation in the region, in a historical key.

2. Methodology

This methodology section of this article describes the research approaches and techniques employed to explore the historical development of legal regulation in the Middle Eastern business sector during the period 1950-1999. Our analysis is based on two main methodologies: the historical method and hermeneutics. These methodologies have been chosen for their relevance and potential to provide a comprehensive understanding of the evolution of business regulation in this region, providing data on the legislative frameworks, policies and major regulated firms of the period.

Following Marc Bloch (2024) and the postulates of the early Annales school, the historical method forms the backbone of our research, facilitating a systematic investigation of the chronological development of legal regulations affecting the Middle Eastern business sector. This method allows us to identify, collect, evaluate and synthesize relevant historical data from a variety of sources, such as: legal documents, archival records, government reports and first-hand accounts.

The objective was to historically reconstruct the socio-economic and political contexts in which these regulations were enacted and to understand their impact on the business environment of the time. Hermeneutics, the art and science of interpreting texts in context, complements the historical method by providing a deeper insight into the meaning and significance of legal texts and policies (Gadamer, 2004). This method emphasizes understanding the intentions behind legal norms, the interpretive frameworks of lawmakers, and the socio-political contexts that shaped those interpretations. Gadamer's hermeneutics involves a critical analysis of texts to uncover the philosophies, ideologies, and goals underlying their messages.

Definitely, the integration of the historical and hermeneutic methods allows for a multi-dimensional exploration of the development of legal regulation in the Middle Eastern business sector. While the historical method provides a structured chronological account, the hermeneutic offers depth and nuance, enriching the understanding of the motivations and consequences of legal changes. Together, these methods facilitate a comprehensive interpretation that not only traces the key stages of business regulation, but also provides a critical assessment of its meaning and legacy.

3. Main research findings

The study of the historical evolution of the legal regulation of the business sector in the countries of the Middle East, from 1950 to 1999, is a complex and multi-faceted problem, historically determined by the specificities of regional development and its dynamics, global political upheavals and transformations, as well as economic ambitions dictated by the development of financial resources. In this historical period, one can trace the emergence of new state formations, triggered by events such as the Cold War, the so-called "oil boom", as well as the globalization of the world economy (Rist, 2008).

Thus, in the 1950s in the countries of the Middle East a wave of decolonizing tendencies and the formation of new states can be traced. Moreover, during these years, states such as Egypt, under the leadership of Abdel Nasser, began to implement bold and reforming nationalization and land reform projects directly related to enterprise development in these territories. For example, the Land Reform Law passed in 1952 in Egypt regulated the complete redistribution of land among farmers. At the same time, this law had a number of critical consequences for the agricultural sector and the implementation of new land tenure models. These reforms were only part of a major socialist policy, the implementation of which was aimed at creating a new system of regulation and supervision of the economy in the form of active government intervention for the achievement of the country's comprehensive development.

During the 1960s and 1970s, the Middle East played a key role in all the world's energy markets, and vigorous oil production only enhanced this role. Given the importance of this energy resource, countries such as Saudi Arabia, Iran and Iraq introduced new legal rules to regulate the use of oil, which subsequently led to the nationalization of oil companies and the development of a state monopoly over this resource. In the 1960s, the activities of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) became key to the development of most Middle Eastern countries and Venezuela, setting national and international trends in the regulation of the energy sector, as well as having a significant impact on the legal regulation of the business sector in the member countries of this Vienna-based organization.

More specifically, the 1970s were marked by the establishment of a policy of economic liberalization in several Middle Eastern countries. For example, Anwar Sadat's Infitah policy in Egypt, initiated in 1974, marked the beginning of a move away from Nasser's socialist paradigm. This legal framework and reform were intended to create an attractive environment for investment, which was reflected in the removal of restrictions on private business and, at the same time, opened up the possibility of attracting foreign investment. Under the influence of these reforms and new regulations in Egypt, during these times, the arrival of transnational companies in the domestic markets can be traced, which further reinforced the liberalization phenomenon (Khatib *et al.*, 2002).

In the 1980s, the Iran-Iraq war (1980-1988) had a dominant influence, with significant negative consequences, both for the region's business sector and for all the economic systems of the countries that directly or indirectly suffered the consequences of this war. The military actions forced each country involved in the conflict to accept and implement emergency stabilization measures and legal support for the economy in crisis situations. For example, Iraq adopted a series of laws that allowed it to attract foreign investment to develop its war-torn economy; while Iran opted for a different vector of legal development: strict national control of resources critical to the economy.

The late 1980s and early 1990s were marked by the growing influences of globalization and the formation of neoliberal policies around the world. The countries of the Middle East

were no exception to this trend. Thus, several countries in this region formed and implemented at this time legal support for the deeper integration of their own economic systems into the world economy, i.e., into the market economy dominated by the hegemonic West. This was expressed in the adoption of new reforms that transformed the economies of the countries according to the type of market. For example, in Jordan, a package of reforms aimed at liberalizing the legal and public sphere, as well as expanding business opportunities and privatizing state-owned enterprises was adopted in 1989 (Bitsani, 2020).

In the 1990s, the signing of the Oslo Agreement between Israel and the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) (1993) had indirect consequences for the business sector and its legal regulation in the territories defined in the aforementioned treaty. The proclamation of the Palestinian Authority led to the formation of a new legal framework and the regulation of business activities in the territories in order to attract foreign investment and stimulate economic development.

In 1981, the Gulf Cooperation Council came to dominate the Middle East scene and for many years assumed the role of setting public policy priorities and legal regulation of the business sectors of its member states. One of the priority areas of activity of this organization was the optimization of each country's trade legislation. An example of this is the Single Economic Agreement, adopted in 1981, with the aim of creating a single market among member states. This agreement facilitated trade communications and investment activity of the parties for many years.

The historical trajectory of the development of legal support in Turkey, a country located on the border between the Middle East and Europe, is interesting. In the 1980s, under the leadership of Turgut Özal, a series of liberalizing reforms aimed at optimizing imports, encouraging foreign investment and developing private enterprise in general were introduced (Zaporozhchenko *et al.*, 2023).

Thus, as can be seen from the general historical analysis up to the end of the 1990s, the legal regulation of the business sector in a number of Middle Eastern countries, such as Palestine, Jordan and Egypt, has undergone significant changes under the influence of internal dynamics as well as a number of globalization factors. In this regard, countries in the region have adopted a combination of protectionist policies and liberal reforms. In this context, we have systematized different approaches to economic development and integration into the world economy (Table 2).

Within this chronological framework, studying the Jordanian approach to business regulation between 1950 and 1999 is crucial for several reasons. Jordan's unique geopolitical situation, historical and political dynamics, and economic strategies provide valuable insight into the broader context of economic development and legal regulation in the Middle East. Unlike some of its resource-rich neighbors, Jordan has had to navigate its economic path with limited natural resources, which makes its legal and economic policies particularly in-

teresting for the study of its historical uniqueness. Through the lens of historical method and hermeneutics, we systematize the evolution of business regulation in Jordan, understanding the socio-political and economic contexts that shaped these laws and policies (Table 3).

Table 2. Positive and negative aspects after historical analysis

Positives Aspects	Negative Aspects
Legal reforms aimed at economic liberalization in countries such as Egypt and Jordan, as well as the establishment of free trade zones in the Gulf States, facilitated economic diversification beyond oil. These reforms attracted foreign investment, stimulated the growth of the private sector, and contributed to economic growth and diversification of the productive apparatus.	While legal reforms aimed at liberalization and privatization stimulated economic growth, they also led to an increase in social inequality in some cases. The rapid changes adversely affected certain segments of the population, particularly those working in sectors affected by privatization or those who lacked the necessary expertise in the new economic environment.
The establishment of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) in 1981 and efforts to harmonize trade laws among member states improved regional economic integration. This cooperation aimed to create a unified economic space, facilitating trade and investment throughout the Persian Gulf region, representing a positive geopolitical step towards regional unity.	Despite diversification efforts, many countries remain heavily dependent on oil revenues. This dependency made their economies vulnerable to fluctuations in world oil prices, affecting their legal and economic stability.
The development and modernization of legal frameworks generally provided a more predictable environment for business operations. Countries that introduced legal reforms to attract foreign investment created a legal infrastructure that supported economic development, technology transfer, and skills acquisition.	The ambitious legal reforms introduced by a number of countries faced difficulties in their implementation. In some cases, lack of institutional capacity, corruption or political resistance hampered the effective implementation of the new laws, limiting their intended economic impact.

Source: (Authors).

Table 3. Evolution of business regulations in Jordan

Period	Name	Characteristics
1950s and 1960s	Fundamentals and Early Development	In the early years of this period, Jordan, like many newly independent states, focused on building the foundations of a modern nation-state. The country's legal framework for business was in its early stages, heavily influenced by the legacy of British mandate laws and early attempts to create a national identity. Business regulation was minimal, and was mainly aimed at encouraging domestic entrepreneurship, within the constraints of a developing economy.
1970s	Regional Challenges and Initial Reforms	The 1970s brought significant challenges and opportunities for Jordan, including the ramifications of regional conflicts. The influx of Palestinian refugees after the 1967 Arab-Israeli war had a significant impact on Jordan's economy and society. In response, Jordan began implementing initial economic reforms to adapt to this demographic shift, focusing on developing a stronger and more coherent legal framework for businesses to stimulate economic growth and provide employment opportunities.

Period	Name	Characteristics
1980s	Economic liberalization and structural adjustment	The 1980s marked a significant shift towards economic liberalization in Jordan, influenced by global trends and the advice of international financial institutions. The country embarked on a structural adjustment program recommended by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank, which included legal reforms aimed at deregulating the economy, encouraging private sector development, and attracting foreign investment. During this period, new laws and regulations were introduced to liberalize trade, facilitate business licensing procedures and provide incentives for foreign investors.
1990s	Further liberalization and integration into the world economy	The 1990s continued the trend of economic liberalization and reform and, in this context, Jordan made significant progress in integrating its economy into the world market.

Source: (Authors).

Figure 2. A model of the application of historical experience of the most important factors in the legal regulation of the business in Jordan.

Source: (Authors).

The signing of the peace treaty with Israel in 1994 was a turning point for Jordan, not only politically but also economically. It led to greater economic cooperation with Western countries and opened new avenues for trade and investment. The treaty was accompanied by legal reforms aimed at improving the business environment, further encouraging foreign direct investment (FDI) and facilitating cross-border trade. Throughout the 1990s, Jordan accelerated its privatization program, selling off state-owned telecommunications, transportation and utility companies. These measures were part of broader economic reforms that included fiscal reforms, liberalization of the financial sector and promotion of the private sector as an engine of economic growth. Legal frameworks were updated to facilitate these changes, aimed at improving efficiency, attracting investment and promoting economic diversification (Shakhatreh *et al.*, 2023).

On this basis, we systematize the historical development of the philosophy of law and legal regulation in the Middle East (Fig. 2).

In conclusion, the period from 1950 to 1999 saw significant transformations in the legal regulation of the business sector in the Middle East, driven by political changes, economic ambitions and global trends. Through historical and hermeneutical analysis, it becomes clear that this legal evolution was not linear, but dialectically determined by the interplay of national priorities, regional dynamics and international influences.

4. Discussion of results

The results of our study on the historical evolution of legal regulation in the Middle Eastern business sector, focusing on the period from 1950 to 1999, present a comprehensive overview of the significant legal frameworks, policies, and business entities that shaped the economic landscape of the region during the second half of the twentieth century. By employing the historical method and hermeneutics, the research provides a nuanced view of the evolution of business regulation in a specific Middle Eastern context, which we compare here with the findings of a selection of references.

Abbasi (1993) analyzes entrepreneurial success in the Middle East with an emphasis on cultural and socio-political factors. Our research complements Abbasi's findings by providing a detailed historical account of how specific legal regulations emerged in response to these cultural and sociopolitical dynamics, especially in Jordan. In contrast to Abbasi's broader analysis, our study delves deeper into the difficulties of legal changes, illustrating how these adjustments facilitated or hindered entrepreneurial success.

Bitsani (2020) explores facets of Arab culture and their implications for business. Our study aligns with Bitsani's cultural perspective, but extends the discussion to the legal realm, showing how cultural considerations influenced legal regulations and, in turn, business practices. The historical method and hermeneutics used in this scholarly article offer a deeper understanding of the cultural underpinnings of legal changes.

Similarly, Alazzam *et al.*, (2023) investigates the formation of an innovative model for the development of e-commerce as part of ensuring business economic security. While Alazzam *et al.*, focus on contemporary e-commerce, our historical analysis highlights the legal underpinnings that are likely to have influenced the evolution of modern e-commerce practices in the Middle East. Understanding the historical development of legal regulations provides context for the challenges and opportunities facing e-commerce in the region.

Khatib *et al.*, (2002) examine business ethics in the Arab Gulf States, identifying challenges and ethical practices. The present research provides a historical backdrop to these ethical considerations by tracing the development of legal frameworks that supported or represented challenges to ethical business practices. The temporal depth of our study provides a context for understanding the persistence of certain ethical issues in business. Otherwise, Godley and Shechter (2008) provide an introduction to the history of business and the Middle East, highlighting the importance of local contexts in multinational responses. Broadly speaking, our research contributes directly to this discourse by detailing how legal regulations have responded to and shaped local business contexts. By focusing on Jordan, we provide a case study that reflects broader regional trends while highlighting the unique historical evolution of legal regulation in a particular country.

Malakhov *et al.*, (2021) and Ortynskiy *et al.*, (2022) analyze the mythologization of law by historical consciousness and the characteristics of philosophical and legal paradigms, respectively. While these studies delve into theoretical aspects of law and history, our research offers a concrete analysis of how historical events and cultural paradigms have been translated into legal regulations affecting the business sector. This practical approach to legal evolution complements the theoretical discussions presented by Malakhov *et al.* and Ortynskiy *et al.* by grounding their broader philosophical investigations in concrete historical cases of legal change. In summary, we have identified the main innovations of our study (Table 3).

Table 3. Main contributions and innovations of this research

Results	Characteristics
Integration of historical and hermeneutical methods	One of the main innovations of our study lies in the integrated application of the historical method and hermeneutics to analyze the legal regulations that affect the business sector. This two-pronged approach allows for a comprehensive examination of the evolution of legal frameworks, taking into account both the chronological progression and the deeper meanings and implications of legal texts in their original context. This methodological innovation enriches the analysis by discovering how historical events, cultural norms, and socio-political dynamics have influenced legal changes and business practices over time.

Results	Characteristics
Analysis focused on legal developments and trade impacts in Jordan	While the existing literature often looks at the Middle East broadly or focuses on more recent developments in business and e-commerce, our study narrows the geographic and temporal scope to provide an in-depth analysis of Jordan's legal regulatory changes, from 1950 to 1999. This approach is innovative in that it details the specific laws, policies, and regulated companies that shaped Jordan's business sector during the second half of the 20th century. By concentrating on Jordan, the study not only contributes to the understanding of the country's legal and economic history, but also serves as a case study that can reflect broader regional trends, offering insight into the challenges and opportunities faced by businesses due to legal developments.
Historical Contextualization of Legal Regulations and Economic Development	The present research innovates by explicitly linking the historical development of legal regulations to the broader context of economic development and diversification in the Middle East, with a special focus on Jordan. In doing so, the article sheds light on the strategic role of legal frameworks in facilitating or hindering economic growth and diversification and integration into the global economy. This innovation provides a valuable historical perspective for policymakers, academics, and business leaders interested in the interplay between legal regulation and economic development.

Source: (Authors).

The detailed analysis of the historical evolution of legal regulation in the Middle East, and in particular in Jordan, enriches the existing literature by providing a focused analysis of the history of legal changes and their impact on business practices. By comparing our results with those of a selection of references, we highlight the unique contributions of our research to the understanding of the complex interplay between legal regulation, cultural norms, and business success in the Middle East. This discussion underscores the importance of historical and legal studies in revealing the paths along which the business sector has evolved in the historical region of the Middle East.

Conclusions and recommendations

In summary, the paper examined the historical evolution of legal regulation of the business sector in the Middle East. The study focused on the development of these activities on the ground in Jordan between 1950 and 1999. A clear identification of the time period made it possible to study and systematize in detail the main aspects of the evolution of legal regulation and its impact on the economic system, the business sector and regional development in Jordan. The study used a synthesis of historical method and hermeneutic analysis. As a result, the authors were able to demonstrate the complex structure of interaction between the evolution of legal regulation and the development of the business sector in Jordan, while revealing the historical aspects of business development and adaptation to the economic, social and historical realities of the Middle East.

The study of the historical origins of legal regulation in the business sector in one Middle Eastern country (Jordan) identified a number of key evolutionary stages in this area. Each of these stages was marked by the formation and regulation of key legal acts and policies, which subsequently had a key impact on the development of the business environment, business climate and principles of business culture in Jordan.

The policy and legislative changes identified in the findings were a reflection of the socio-economic trends of the time, mainly related to the phenomena of modernization, the transition to new levels of automation and the influences of globalization, without losing sight of the influence of the unique cultural and political context of the Middle East.

In summary, it was found that this historical period is marked by the adoption of key laws and regulations related to accelerating the pace of economic development, improving the level of investment attractiveness and increasing trade relations. Today, the full regulation of this legal framework in Jordan makes it possible to trace the phenomena of economic diversification and growth, which is an argument confirming the key role of this legal regulation in the formation of optimal conditions for economic development and business.

Although this study provides a glimpse into the future of legal regulation in Jordan, it has limitations. Thus, the study faces a geographical limitation in that only one country in the Middle East has been taken as the object of analysis. This limitation, on the one hand, allows for a better analysis of the historical origins of legal and business development in Jordan, but, on the other hand, it may result in restricted and imprecise exposure when extrapolating the results obtained to other countries in the Middle East. This limitation is largely due to the specific characteristics of the economic, political, business and social life of each country, which have led to different trajectories of the historical development of the legal regulation of the business sector in each of them.

But it should be noted that this limitation does not have a negative impact on the results of the study and does not detract from its importance for the future development of the legal regulation of the business sector in Jordan. This limitation justifies the prospects and importance of further research that expands the geographical boundaries of the historical analysis of the legal regulation of the business sector, including new countries and their histories of development in this field.

Finally, it is also important to note the importance of expanding the historical framework of the study to include the last period of the 21st century, as it has become a period of dramatic changes, global upheavals and major technological advances. All these phenomena have led to significant changes in the legal regulation of the business sector in Jordan and other Middle Eastern countries. Expanding the historical framework of the study will not only allow us to better understand the current situation, but also to more effectively formulate a forecast of the evolution of legal regulation of the business sector.

The historical development of legal regulation in the business sector in the Middle East between 1950 and 1999 has been influenced by several factors, including industrialization, economic globalization, and the evolution of fiscal and monetary policies. During this period, accelerated economic growth was observed in Asia, especially in China, which was characterized by gradual price liberalization, cautious creation of property rights, and experimentation in trade openness.

In the Middle East, economic growth was less homogeneous and was affected by conflicts and crises in some countries. The world economy experienced progressive growth, although not uniformly in different regions. During this period, Europe and North America experienced significant economic growth, while Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean experienced slower growth.

In terms of legal regulation, there was an increase in international cooperation on issues such as environmental protection and sustainable development. The 1992 Rio de Janeiro Summit reached a consensus on the transfer of technologies and financial resources required by developing countries, recognizing that environmental protection and economic development require global solutions.

Definitely, during the period from 1950 to 1999, the historical development of legal regulation in the business sector in the Middle East was influenced by industrialization, economic globalization and the evolution of fiscal and monetary policies. Accelerated economic growth was observed in Asia, especially in China, but with different results in different regions. In addition, there was an increase in international cooperation on issues such as environmental protection and sustainable development.

Finally, the results obtained allow us to make the following recommendations:

1. To deepen research on contemporary history of the Middle East, as a condition of possibility to overcome the thematic and problematic gaps that identify the specialized literature on the subject.
2. To build interdisciplinary theoretical and methodological frameworks that contribute new or renewed perspectives of analysis on issues such as legal regulation in the business sector.
3. To create epistemological bridges between the historical science cultivated in Ibero-America and the Middle East, especially when academic relations between the two regions have been distant and occasional.

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